

YUSUF HAMADONIY THE GREAT SHEIKH OF SUFISM

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Annotation: In the article, it was spoken about Abdulkholiq Ghijduvoniyy and there was analyzed his work “Maqamoti Yusuf Hamadoniyy”, which he devoted to his master. This paper also draws attention to the fact that, along with giving valuable information about Yusuf Hamadoniyy’s life and activities, there are some problematic information and the author’s own point of view about its reasons is given.

Key words: Sufism, Hoja Abdulkholiq Ghijduvoniyy, "Maqomoti Yusuf Hamadani".

Khoja Abdulkholiq ibn Abduljamil Ghijduvoniyy, the great figure of Sufism, the famous saint, the founder and leader of the Central Asian sect and known with the name “Khojagon”, was born in 1103 in the village of Ghijduvon, one of the largest commercial caravan routes near Bukhara, in a well-educated family. Having received the first information in his village, he goes to Bukhara to improve his education at the age of 22. Here he receives sufficient knowledge from the great scholars of that time and Sufism. Particularly, his meeting with the famous Sufi leader, Abu Yaqub Yusuf Hamadoniyy (1140 AD), played an important role. Yusuf Hamadoniyy attracted him to Sufism. Yusuf Hamadoniyy was born in Ghanimiya, the city of Hamadon, Iran, in 440 AD 1048 (according to some data in 1049)[1]. He died in 1141 AD. His grave is situated close to the pilgrimage place of Sultan Sanjar in Marv. People of Sufism praises Yusuf Hamadoniyy’s mausoleum as “Kabai-Khurasan (Caaba of Khurasan)”.

In his time, Yusuf Hamadoniyy was a Shaykhush shuyukh – sheikh of sheikhs, a scholar of the Rabbani-Divine Sciences, kutbi asar – defender of his century, sohibkaromat avliyo – a saint who is famous for his sacred saints, an owner of spiritual maturity, piri murshid – irshod i.e. ecclesiastic preceptor educating a person who can have the right to teach others.

Abdulkholiq Ghijduvoniyy described Yusuf Hamadoniyy, his piri murshid in his book “Maqomoti Yusuf Hamadoniyy”. Abdulkholiq Ghijduvoniyy’s book “Maqomoti Yusuf Hamadoniyy” includes the following parts called as the preface, the blessed admonitions of Yusuf Hamadoniyy, the letter of Sanjar ibn Malikshah, the birth and morality of the sheikh, the sheikh's arrival to Samarkand and the history of the sheikh’s death. Indeed, in this work there are also facts about the Ghijduvoniyy’s biography, as well as about the murids (apprentices) of Yusuf Hamadoniyy. However, the main purpose of writing this book was to make people aware of His Majesty Yusuf Hamadoniyy’s morals, stories, wisdom and the great services he had performed in history.

In his “Maqamoti Yusuf Hamadoniyy”, Abdulkholiq Ghijduvoniyy, narrated his masters’ every deeds and every sayings watching them all the time. It should be noted that His Majesty Yusuf Hamadoniyy visited and studied in Bukhara, Samarkand Marv (Mori), Khorezm, Baghdad, Mecca, Medina and other cities. It is written in the sources that His Majesty was a interlocutor of two hundred and thirteen great scholars, Sheikhs. In “Maqamoti Yusuf Hamadoniyy”, there was offered the genealogy of His Majesty Hamadoniyy and it was noted that he was a leader in sciences of hadis (legend about Prophet Mohammed) and tafsir and the leader of theory. In his work “Maqamoti Yusuf Hamadoniyy”, Abdulkholiq Ghijduvoniyy narrates the following story about his master with great respect: “One day, His Majesty Yusuf Hamadoniyy looked at me and said, 'As I am the fourth caliph of Khojai Kalon (i.e. Formadiyy), you are my fourth caliph'. Then his eyes filled with tears. I asked, “Who could be a caliph instead of you?” Sheikh said: ‘Hey Abdulkholiq, on my place there will be Abdullo Barkiyy, then Khoja Hasan Andoqiyy and then Khoja Ahmad Yassaviyy. Khoja Ahmad Yassaviyy will travel to Turkistan, and you will become caliph instead. And follow the Sahriat’s (Muslim code of religious, criminal and civil laws based on the Koran) rules all the time and do not disobey the Shariat and prohibit if you see whoever commits an act that is contrary to Shariat”.

Abdulkholiq Ghijduvoni stated that His Majesty Yusuf Hamadoni went on hadj (pilgrimage to the sacred cities of Mecca and Medina) on foot, read the Koran 1000 times and learnt by heart 700 books about tafsir, hadith, fiqh, usul, furu and kalam. More than seven hundred apprentices of his from all over the world reached the level of divinity. In the works, the following facts were interestingly illustrated that Yusuf Hamadani often kept fast during day time and prayed during night, therefore eight hundred people of Buddha religion accepted Islam and very many people found the way of the Truth.

The clever student mentions with great respect that his blessed master was a scientist in conversations and circles; he would never say he was a saint in the circles, he did never prevailed himself over others, he did not insult or deride anyone and he applied everybody as “Khoja!” whoever he saw”.

Abdulkholiq Ghijduvoni describes some of his teacher’s precepts as follows: He said “Hush dar dam” (be careful of every breath, be careful not to be inattentive), “nazar bar qadam” (look under your feet and straight to avoid sin and neglect) “Safar dar vatan” (travel in the country) and “Hilvat dar anjuman” (be with people externally and be with reality internally). In his outer and inner world, he sat with modesty, bow and honor ... Sometimes he said: “Hey kings and dignitaries, ignorant people, you are ignorant of the spiritual pleasures of dervishes. Enjoy others with the language quotes. Try to know passion and find out what’s going to happen in soul. Liberate your outer world from distresses because his inner world will be even more dispersed whose outer world is scattered”.

I. Muminov separately emphasizes that Sufism appeared in the 8th century as a philosophical doctrine and entered Mavarounnahr through Iran and had a great influence here in 11th and 12th centuries. Also, when evaluating Sufism as a sophisticated philosophic aspect, the scholar states that there are various trends and directions in it, that the study of Sufism requires a special study and that the most important aspects of Sufism are to be analyzed[9]. The scholar states that Sufism started to spread in Movarounnahr, including the territory of present-day Uzbekistan in the second half of the 11th century and the beginning of the 12th century, i.e. during

the period of feudal wars and nomadic tribal aggression. According to V.V. Bartold's book "Turkiston madaniy hayoti tarixi (History of Turkestan's Cultural Life)", the flow of Sufism in Movarounnahr started from the school of the 12th century thinker, Yusuf Hamadoni. I. Muminov noted that Yusuf Hamadoni's school had no uniformity, where different streams were observed and he comments that the greatest streams among them were two. In particular, Yusuf Hamadoni and Abdulkholiq Ghijduvoni's teachings of Sufism corresponded to the interests of city workers. I. Muminov acknowledges that there are basic rules containing "hush dar dam, nazar bar qadam, safar dar vatan, hilvat dar anjuman", which corresponded to exactly urban people.

I. Muminov, while emphasizing that Yusuf Hamadoni had a proficiency of shoemaker, he directly participated in defending Bukhara and Samarkand from the attacks of nomadic tribes, separately explains that Yusuf Hamadoni called on his students to work and to acquire a profession. The scientist came to conclusion that it is not possible to say that this stream (i.e. the direction of khojagon N.N.) was a mystical stream of Sufism and that it played a progressive role in the development of literary and social thought in its time. Such positive conclusions emphasized by the scientist about the Sufism with a great braveness during the reign of the soviet ideology, help to logically approach to the issue in this article.

Abdulkholiq Ghijduvoni's "Maqomoti Yusuf Hamadoni" is very valuable as a sign of great respect to his master Yusuf Hamadoni. The life of these great people is a great school of edification and the spiritual heritage left by them to the generations serve to further develop spiritual mind of our nation. It is necessary to make scientific conclusions being based on a historical method and a logical approach in studying this book.

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